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**IN SILICO IDENTIFICATION OF MICRORNAS POTENTIALLY REGULATING
THE *SCN1A* GENE INVOLVED IN GENETIC EPILEPSY**

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Annotation. *This study focuses on the in-silico identification of microRNAs (miRNAs) potentially regulating the *SCN1A* gene, which encodes the NaV1.1 sodium channel α -subunit and plays a crucial role in neuronal excitability and genetic epilepsy. Using the miRDB database, 246 candidate miRNAs were predicted to target *SCN1A*, with confidence scores ranging from 50 to 97. Among the top candidates were hsa-miR-150-3p, hsa-miR-30e-5p, hsa-miR-548ah-5p, and hsa-miR-106b-5p, previously linked to neuronal differentiation and synaptic signaling. Functional analysis indicated their enrichment in ion transport and synaptic regulation pathways, suggesting their involvement in epileptogenesis. The obtained results provide a computational basis for understanding post-transcriptional regulation of *SCN1A* and may support the discovery of new miRNA-based biomarkers and therapeutic targets for *SCN1A*-related epileptic disorders.*

Key words: *SCN1A, miRNA, Dravet syndrome, sodium channel, epilepsy, in silico analysis, miRDB.*

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent seizures caused by abnormal neuronal excitability [1]. Genetic epilepsies have attracted great interest due to mutations and post-transcriptional dysregulation in ion channel-coding genes. Among them, *SCN1A* is one of the most critical, encoding the NaV1.1 sodium channel α -subunit that maintains inhibitory GABAergic neuron activity [2]. Dysregulation or mutation of *SCN1A* leads to neuronal hyperexcitability and seizure susceptibility, being closely associated with Dravet syndrome and GEFS+. Recent studies indicate that *SCN1A* expression may also be modulated by microRNAs (miRNAs), small non-coding RNAs that regulate gene expression at the post-transcriptional level, suggesting their potential involvement in the molecular pathogenesis of genetic epilepsy [2].

In the present study, an *in silico* analysis was conducted to identify potential miRNAs that could regulate *SCN1A* expression using the miRDB database (<https://mirdb.org/cgi-bin/search.cgi>). The miRDB algorithm applies a machine-learning model trained on high-throughput experimental data to predict miRNA-mRNA interactions and assign each target pair a confidence score.

The *in silico* analysis identified 246 candidate miRNAs predicted to target the *SCN1A* gene, with scores ranging from 50 to 97. Among the top candidates were hsa-miR-150-3p, hsa-miR-548ah-5p, hsa-miR-30a-5p, hsa-miR-30e-5p, and hsa-miR-106b-5p, several of which are involved in neurogenesis, synaptic signaling, and neuroinflammatory regulation. Functional enrichment analysis showed their association with ion transport, synaptic transmission, and neuronal excitability, which are key mechanisms in epileptogenesis. These findings provide insight into the post-transcriptional regulation of *SCN1A* and highlight miRNA candidates for further *in vitro* validation. The results offer a computational framework for exploring miRNA-based biomarkers and therapeutic targets in *SCN1A*-related genetic epilepsies.

REFERENCES

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